

Strelitzia alba Cape wild banana

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

© G.J. Mann

Estimated genome size: 739 million DNA base pairs (0.74 Gigabases)

Organism size: Up to 2 meters in height

Distribution:

Strelitzia alba has a restricted range, occurring along South Africa's Garden Route in the coastal forests of the Western Cape and Eastern Cape. It thrives in evergreen forests, gorges, and river slopes.

Importance:

The white-flowered wild banana or Cape wild banana is a striking plant endemic to South Africa's Garden Route. It plays an important ecological role in its forest habitat. Although classified as not endangered, wild populations face pressure from harvesting seeds and side shoots for cultivation. Its distinctive white flowers make it a sought-after species, contributing to its commercial and conservation significance.

PromethION Sequencing Report: Output: 39.29 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 5.04 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome length: 530.29 million bases (0.53 Gigabases)

BUSCO completeness score (single and duplicated genes): 99.2%

[Single: 58.4%, Duplicated: 40.8%]

Sample Contributor contact details

Prof. Eshchar Mizrachi

University of Pretoria

eshchar.mizrachi@fabi.up.ac.za